

Original article

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IDENTIFICATION OF INFLATION ATTENTION REGIME IN SERBIA

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Abstract: *Inflation is one of the main macroeconomic issues that individuals and policymakers observe. However, not all levels of inflation trigger the same interest of public. Naturally, there are two substantially different regimes, i.e. low inflation attention, and high inflation attention regime. These regimes are identified in Serbia based on the available monthly data from 2011M1 to 2025M5. Data are extracted from Google searches of word “inflation” in Serbian and normalized to the month with the most Google searches of that word. Based on available data, we used the following common statistical methodology used in literature to make the distinction between the regimes. Months with the high attention regime are those when Google searches for inflation in that month exceeds the 75th percentile. Otherwise, low inflation attention regime emerges. One of the crucial insights is that negative supply side shocks are significant drivers of inflation attention. Identification of these regimes has high importance for monetary policymaking, due to the strong interdependence with inflation expectations and ultimately with the Consumer Price Index (CPI) measured inflation rate. Anchoring inflation expectations is conditio sine qua non of inflation stabilization, and success on that partially depend on inflation (in)attention.*

Keywords: *Inflation attention, inflation rate, inflation expectations, monetary policy, Serbia.*